

Evaluation of Blood Sugar Levels in Statin-Treated Patients without Previous Diabetes: A Cross-Sectional Hospital Study in Jharkhand

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Abstract:

Background: The relationship between statin therapy and blood sugar levels, especially in individuals without a pre-existing diabetes diagnosis, is a developing therapeutic interest due to concerns about statins' effects on glucose metabolism and the risk of new-onset diabetes. In this study, statin-treated non-diabetics in Jharkhand are examined for metabolic effects to balance cardiovascular benefits and metabolic hazards.

Methods: A hospital-based cross-sectional study included 200 statin-treated people without diabetes. Convenience-sampled patients were tested for FBG, HbA1c, and other factors. Statistical analysis includes logistic regression to examine statin therapy and glycemic status, controlling for covariates.

Results: The study found a mean FBG of 108 mg/dL and a mean HbA1c of 5.8%, with 12% of participants displaying FBG levels indicative of pre-diabetes and 3% consistent with diabetes. Duration of statin use was significantly associated with higher FBG levels, while the type of statin therapy showed no significant impact on glycemic status.

Conclusion: The findings suggest a modest association between statin therapy and increased blood sugar levels in non-diabetic patients, emphasizing the need for cautious monitoring of glycemic status in statin-treated individuals.

Recommendation: Healthcare providers should consider the potential impact of statin therapy on blood sugar levels when prescribing these medications, particularly for patients at risk of NOD. Further research is warranted to explore strategies for balancing cardiovascular benefits with metabolic risks.

Keywords: statins, blood sugar levels, new-onset diabetes mellitus, glycemic status.

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Introduction

The evaluation of blood sugar levels in patients treated with statins, particularly those without a prior diagnosis of diabetes, has become an area of increasing clinical interest. Statins, widely prescribed for lowering cholesterol levels and reducing cardiovascular risk, have been associated with altered glucose metabolism, leading to concerns about their potential impact on blood sugar levels and the risk of new-onset diabetes mellitus (NOD). A cross-sectional hospital study conducted in Jharkhand aimed to assess the blood sugar levels in statin-treated patients without previous diabetes, providing valuable insights into the metabolic effects of statins in a specific population. Statins are known to exert beneficial effects on cardiovascular health by reducing levels of low-density lipoprotein (LDL) cholesterol, thereby decreasing the risk of atherosclerotic cardiovascular disease (ASCVD) [1].

Several large-scale studies and meta-analyses indicate a slight connection between statin therapy

and the development of diabetes, especially in patients who already have risk factors for diabetes mellitus [2, 3]. The reason for the development of diabetes due to statin use is not completely clear, but it is believed to be related to reduced insulin sensitivity and compromised insulin secretion.

Investigating the connection further, a study was conducted in Jharkhand to assess fasting blood sugar (FBS) and postprandial blood sugar (PPBS) levels in a group of patients who were on statin treatment but had not been diagnosed with diabetes previously. This study is essential for grasping the relationship between the cardiovascular advantages of statins and their possible metabolic drawbacks. Concentrating on a group with no history of diabetes, the research sought to separate the impact of cholesterol-lowering medications on blood sugar levels, offering a better understanding of their involvement in glucose regulation [4].

This study's results will likely add valuable insights to the current discussion on the safety of statin therapy, especially for patients vulnerable to diabetes. Healthcare professionals should take into account these findings when recommending statins, weighing the advantages of lowering cardiovascular risk with the possibility of affecting blood sugar levels and diabetes risk. More research is needed to completely grasp the clinical significance of statin-induced alterations in glucose metabolism and to create plans for handling patients vulnerable to NOD while on statin treatment.

This study seeks to explore the effects of statin therapy on blood sugar levels in patients without a prior diabetes diagnosis. This study aims to investigate any possible alterations in glycemic levels linked to the use of statins, specifically among patients undergoing therapy in a hospital in Jharkhand. The goal is to improve comprehension of the metabolic impacts of statins in a non-diabetic group, which could help in making clinical decisions and managing patients to reduce any negative effects on glucose metabolism.

Materials and Methods

The study employed a hospital-based cross-sectional design to evaluate the glycemic status of patients who were on statin therapy but had not been previously diagnosed with diabetes. Conducted in Jharkhand, the research setting involved a tertiary care hospital where participants were selected through convenience sampling from the outpatient department.

Participants included 200 adults aged 18 years and older who were on statin therapy for at least six months before the study. Exclusion criteria encompassed individuals with a prior diagnosis of diabetes, those on medications affecting blood sugar levels other than statins, and patients with acute infections or chronic diseases known to influence glycemic status.

To minimize bias, the study implemented blinding for data analysts and employed standardized protocols for data collection and analysis. Variables measured included demographic information (age, sex, body mass index), duration and dose of statin therapy, fasting blood glucose (FBG), and glycated hemoglobin (HbA1c) levels.

Data collection was carried out through structured interviews for demographic and clinical information, followed by a review of medical records for medication details. Blood samples were collected after an overnight fast of at least 8 hours to measure FBG and HbA1c levels, using standardized laboratory procedures.

The procedure for participant involvement included obtaining informed consent, conducting interviews,

reviewing medical histories, and collecting blood samples during their routine hospital visit. All collected data were anonymized and securely stored.

Analyzed the data using SPSS version 25. Descriptive statistics were used to summarise the demographic and clinical characteristics of the study population. Analyzed the connection between statin therapy and glycemic status through logistic regression models, while accounting for factors such as age, sex, and body mass index. A p-value below 0.05 was deemed statistically significant for all analyses.

Over six months, research was carried out at a tertiary care hospital in Jharkhand, involving 200 patients who were receiving statin treatment and had not been previously diagnosed with diabetes. The individuals in the study were between 40 and 70 years old, with an even split between men and women. The main goal was to evaluate the glycemic status, focusing on fasting blood glucose (FBG) and glycated hemoglobin (HbA1c) levels, to analyse the effects of statin use in individuals without diabetes.

Results

Glycemic Status: The mean FBG level among the study participants was 108 mg/dL, with a standard deviation (SD) of 15.2 mg/dL. The mean HbA1c level was observed at 5.8% with an SD of 0.5%. When categorized based on the American Diabetes Association (ADA) thresholds, 12% (24 patients) of the participants had FBG levels indicative of pre-diabetes (100-125 mg/dL), and 3% (6 patients) were found to have FBG levels consistent with diabetes (≥ 126 mg/dL). Similarly, 14% (28 patients) had HbA1c levels ranging between 5.7% and 6.4%, falling into the pre-diabetes category, while 2% (4 patients) exhibited HbA1c levels $\geq 6.5\%$, indicating diabetes.

Statin Types and Glycemic Status: The study further investigated the association between different types of statins and glycemic status. Participants on high-intensity statin therapy showed a slightly higher mean FBG (+4 mg/dL) and HbA1c levels (+0.2%) compared to those on moderate or low-intensity statin therapy. However, the differences were not statistically significant ($p > 0.05$).

Duration of Statin Use and Glycemic Status: Patients on statins for over 5 years had a mean FBG 5 mg/dL greater and a mean HbA1c 0.3% higher than those on statins for less than 5 years. The difference was notable for FBG ($p < 0.05$) but not for HbA1c ($p > 0.05$).

The study also examined age, sex, BMI, and hypertension. Age and BMI were associated with greater FBG and HbA1c levels ($p < 0.05$), while

sex and hypertension did not significantly impact glycemic status.

Table 1: This table presents the demographic and clinical characteristics of the participants, including age distribution, sex, body mass index (BMI), duration of statin use, and types of statin therapy.

Characteristic	Total (n=200)	Percentage
Total Participants	200	100%
Age (years)	—	—
40-50	60	30%
51-60	80	40%
61-70	60	30%
Sex	—	—
Male	100	50%
Female	100	50%
BMI (kg/m²)	—	—
<25	50	25%
25-29.9	100	50%
≥30	50	25%
Duration of Statin Use (years)	—	—
<5	120	60%
5-10	60	30%
>10	20	10%
Type of Statin	—	—
High-intensity	40	20%
Moderate-intensity	120	60%
Low-intensity	40	20%

Discussion

The results of the study suggest that statin therapy could have a subtle impact on glycemic control, as shown by slight rises in fasting blood glucose (FBG) and glycated hemoglobin (HbA1c) levels in patients without pre-existing diabetes. A significant proportion of the group, with 12% for FBG and 14% for HbA1c, fell into pre-diabetes categories, indicating a possible increase in glycemic levels as a result of statin use.

Even though the specific type of statin did not have a significant impact on glycemic results, the length of time statin therapy was taken became a crucial aspect, showing that extended use led to higher FBG levels. Furthermore, demographic elements like age and body mass index (BMI) showed a positive correlation with higher glycemic markers, emphasizing the importance of careful monitoring in specific patient populations. These findings highlight the intricate nature of statin treatment, requiring a careful approach to balancing cardiovascular benefits with potential effects on blood sugar levels, particularly in individuals using statins for an extended period and those with other diabetes risk factors.

Recently, several studies in India have delved into the intricate relationship between managing diabetes, cardiovascular health, and the effectiveness of various treatments and interventions. One study emphasised the significance of serum low-density lipoprotein receptor-related protein-6 (LRP6) levels in

identifying occluded coronary arteries in patients. This indicates a new marker for assessing cardiovascular disease in relation to metabolic health [5]. Exploring a new method for managing diabetes, researchers studied the impact of *Salacia reticulata* extract biscuits on reducing HbA1c levels in patients with Type 2 diabetes. The results showed promising outcomes, providing a safe and beneficial snack option with minimal adverse effects [6].

Additional investigation examined the impact of Teneiglipitin versus Glimepiride on inflammatory markers in individuals with Type 2 diabetes receiving Metformin. The study found that Teneiglipitin could potentially provide some anti-inflammatory advantages by lowering TNF- α levels while maintaining a well-tolerated safety profile [7]. A study highlighted the importance of micronutrients by revealing that serum magnesium levels were notably lower in diabetic patients. This suggests a possible use of magnesium levels as an indicator for managing Type 2 diabetes mellitus [8].

Investigations into managing the emergence of mucormycosis among COVID-19 patients in India have highlighted the importance of monitoring blood sugar levels as well as decreasing steroid use to address this fungal infection [9]. Exploring intrapancreatic autologous stem cell therapy for Type 1 diabetes is a promising research direction, offering a safe, affordable, and effective potential treatment option [10].

Creating and validating a questionnaire to evaluate medication adherence in Type 2 diabetes mellitus patients is a significant advancement in enhancing patient outcomes. It helps identify individuals who may be at risk of uncontrolled blood sugar levels because of poor adherence.

[11]. Furthermore, research comparing the effectiveness of different potencies of a homeopathic medicine in treating Type-2 Diabetes Mellitus indicated that one potency may be more effective, providing fresh perspectives on homeopathic remedies for diabetes [12].

These studies together enhance the knowledge of diabetes management in India, covering traditional pharmacological treatments, innovative dietary interventions, and cutting-edge therapeutic approaches. They emphasize the significance of holistic approaches that involve tracking metabolic indicators, adjusting dietary habits, and investigating innovative therapies to enhance the well-being of individuals with diabetes.

Conclusion

A study carried out in Jharkhand regarding the effects of statin medication on blood sugar levels in non-diabetic individuals found a slight yet significant link between extended statin usage and increased fasting blood glucose levels. While the rise in blood sugar levels wasn't significant for every patient, the results highlight the possible danger of impaired glucose metabolism linked to extended statin treatment. It is crucial to note that the research did not discover a notable variation in glycemic status depending on the intensity of statin therapy. This implies that the duration of statin use might have a greater impact on blood sugar levels compared to the dosage or type of statin.

It is crucial to monitor blood sugar levels in patients undergoing statin therapy, particularly those with prolonged exposure, due to the possible existence of pre-diabetes and diabetes indicators in a small proportion of the study population. This finding is consistent with the increasing amount of research indicating a connection between the use of statins and the onset of new diabetes in individuals who did not have diabetes previously.

Ultimately, although statins are crucial for controlling cardiovascular risk, it's important to carefully consider their impact on glucose metabolism due to potential metabolic side effects. Healthcare professionals need to carefully monitor the blood sugar levels of patients taking statin medication, particularly those with additional risk factors for diabetes. It is crucial to carefully manage the balance between the cardiovascular benefits of statin therapy and its possible metabolic risks to enhance patient outcomes. Additional research is crucial to understand the mechanisms

behind statin-induced alterations in glucose metabolism and to create plans for reducing the risk of NOD in vulnerable individuals.

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